

Table 2. Summary of EWEs and frequency of most common mental health outcomes

EWE (# of studies)	Countries (frequency)	# of unique MH outcomes	Three most common MH outcomes (frequency)
Cyclone (n=3)	Bangladesh (2), India	5	1. Depression (3) 2. Anxiety (2) 3. (tied) Psychological distress; Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD); Suicidal ideation (1 each)
Drought (n=12)	Australia (4), Bangladesh, Botswana (2), Ethiopia, India (3), USA	14	1. Depression (3) 2. (tied) Psychological distress; Suicide deaths; Suicidal ideation; Trauma symptoms (2 each)
Flood (n=41)	Australia (2), Bangladesh (2), Burundi, Canada, China (7), Ghana, India (9), Malaysia (1), Indonesia (5), Pakistan, Spain, Thailand, UK (7), USA (2)	64	1. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (29) 2. Depression (22) 3. Anxiety (17)
Extreme Cold / Cold spells (n=6)	China (4), Sweden, USA	13	1. Mental health ED visits (1) 2. All other outcomes occurred only once
Extreme Heat / Heat waves (n=32)	Australia (3), Belgium, Brazil, Canada, China (7), Finland, India (2), Japan (3), Philippines, South Africa, South Korea (2), Spain (2), Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, UK USA (8), Vietnam (3)	54	1. Mental disorders admissions (8) 2. (tied) Mental health ED visits; Suicide deaths (6 each)
Extreme Rainfall (n=2)	China (2)	4	1. (tied) Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD); Resilience; Rumination; Schizophrenia hospitalizations (1 each)
Hurricane (n=21)	Bahamas, Puerto Rico, USA (19)	36	1. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (8) 2. Depression (5) 3. Anxiety (3)
Snowstorm (n=2)	UK, USA	2	1. (tied) Emotional upheaval; Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (1 each)
Tornado (n=6)^	China (5), USA	9	1. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (4) 2. Mindfulness (3) 3. (tied) Burnout; Depression (2 each)
Typhoon (n=9)	Philippines (8), Taiwan	19	1. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (5) 2. (tied) Acute stress disorder; Depression, anxiety and stress; Posttraumatic cognitions; Psychological distress (2 each)
Wildfire (n=28)	Australia (11), Canada (12), Greece, USA (4)	48	1. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (17) 2. Depression (10) 3. (tied) Anxiety; Major Depressive Disorder (6 each)

^5 of the 6 studies used the same baseline population data; EWE – Extreme weather event, MH – Mental health